

INTERPRETATION OF BABUR'S PERSONALITY IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND INDIAN LITERATURE

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Abstract: This article is based on the interpretation of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's personality in English, Indian and Uzbek literature. During the researches literary works by authors, such as Pirinkul Kadyrov, Khayriddin Sultanov, Flora Anne Steel and Muni La'l are widely analyzed. Description of Babur's personality as a son and brother, husband and father are displayed in a comparative way. Parts of the literary works are included where we can identify personal features of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur.

Key words: Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Amir Temur, Kabul, Mirza, Emperor, Afghanistan, Motherland, Samarkand, Andijan, Khojand.

Babur tried to learn from his grandfather Amir Temur in life. This is expressed in the work of Muni Lal as follows: "Babur always believed that Allah had chosen him to save the state founded by Timur." For this reason, even when he faced great failures, he did not despair. On the contrary, his failures gave him more energy, encouraged him to move forward, to be patient with all those who are destined for his fate. In fact, Babur, who considered himself the true successor of Amir Temur, tried to be stable at all times. Because he believed that his becoming king was not accidental, but chosen to save the state founded by Temur. That's why he was never disappointed. He considered it a sign of fate. H. Sultanov's images are also in line with this: "While wandering around the places where the footsteps of his illustrious ancestor Temurbek were touched or where his immortal legacy spread, he always communicates absently with the owner, seeks comfort from his teachings, and writes down every historical

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information related to him in his heart notebook. respectfully noted. While evaluating the political and moral behavior of the statesmen of his time or those who passed before or after him, His Holiness Babur always takes the activity of Amir Temur as the main criterion. Based on this criterion, he expresses his judgments...". The above picture also confirms that Babur looked at his great-grandfather Amir Temur with great devotion. Even when he was in trouble, he sought solace from Amir Temur's teachings. As a writer Babur was able to impressively reflect the warm and pleasant moments in his heart and soul. That is, it can be seen in such things as his communication with the master in absentia, seeking comfort from his teachers, writing the historical information related to him in his notebook, and considering his work as a criterion for himself.

It is known from historical sources that Zahiriddin Muhammad, after establishing his rule in Kabul, ordered that he be called "king" as a descendant of Temurbek. This reality is interpreted by the Indian writer Muni Lal as follows: "Shaibani Khan and the Mongol invasions were suppressed, and now there was no force left to threaten Babur's rule in Kabul. Now he decides to take the title of "King". At that time, the princes from Temur's generation were called "Mirza" even when they took over the government. Babur, who received the title of "King", was continuing the work of his ancestors. Adib emphasizes the fact that Babur's great ancestor Amir Temur continued his work. In fact, unlike the contemporary Timurids, Babur orders them to call themselves "King" and not "Mirza". Unlike other Timurids, he founded a new Empire. For this reason, he was a person worthy of being called "King" in every way.

The English writer Flora Steele interprets this reality a little differently: "Babur, who was very happy with the birth of his son, was deeply engrossed in the new title of "Emperor" given to him and was busy spending his energetic life force on gathering his troops and fighting battles. His whole day was spent in the military department. Anna Steele justifies Babur's great position in the Western world by calling him "Emperor". Moreover, this word is characteristic of Western culture and mentality. Adiba attributes Babur's assumption of this title to the birth of his first son, Humayun.

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The writer's deep respect for Babur is also noticeable. Because according to his interpretation, despite receiving this title, Babur did not give in to ambition, and on the contrary, he worked on himself, continued military training, and during the day was busy only with exercises in the military department. Historical facts also confirm this.

In the last years of his life, Babur becomes very depressed, he has almost no interest in all the pleasures of life. Muni Lal describes such situations in the psyche of the king-poet as follows: "In the winter days of Agra, he wandered the streets in search of something he did not know, he felt alone and shed tears for his sins. He wanted to go back to Kabul and Samarkand. He missed the melons and grapes of Samarkand, the snowy peaks of Afghanistan." Ever since he lost his country, Babur lived his whole life with love for the Motherland. Homesickness tormented him, especially in the last years of his life. He wanted to visit the cities of Andijan, Samarkand and Kabul, which he ruled for 20 years, to taste the sweet sugar melons and grapes of Samarkand, and to walk on the snowy peaks of Afghanistan. In fact, Muni Lal Babur's emotional experiences were impressively expressed. In these images, the patriotism of the king-poet was clearly demonstrated.

Khayriddin Sultanov expressed this reality as follows: "Babur used to sit alone at the foot of the garden, on the huge mountain porch that rose high among the oleander and laurel trees. In the last years of his life, he had cooled down from the parties and performances in the palace, full of cheerfulness, and the cruel deeds of the Indian dancers, and the charming verses of the nightingale-like poets in the sky of glory, did not bring pleasure to his heart anymore. He spent most of his time out of sight, alone in a secluded corner, only occasionally, when he felt like it, he would call Yusufi and order roses. It is known that in the last years of his life, Babur spent a lot of time in solitude. As it was mentioned above, he was no longer interested in the parties in the palace, the performances of the dancers and the poems of the poets did not give him pleasure. He often spent his time in solitude thinking. In fact, these dreams lead him to the Motherland, he lived with this dream. Author realistically reflected Babur's mental state in moments of loneliness.

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